

Influence of Agricultural Technologies on Youth Livelihood and Employability in Ogun State, Nigeria

¹Abiala, A. A., ²Oladele, M. N., ¹Adeneye, A. S., ³Bamgbowu, S. A., ⁴Olawumi, A. T., ¹Ogunmosu, D. I.,
¹Osipitan, A. O. and ⁵Jolayemi, J. O.

¹Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, ⁴Department of Tourism and Hospitality Management, Tai
Solarin Federal University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State.

²Faculty of Science, Oyo State College of Agriculture and Technology, Igboora

³Department of Agricultural Science Education, Lagos State University of Education, Noforija.

⁵Department of Agricultural Science Education, Kwara State College of Education, Oro.

Corresponding Email: abialaaa@tasued.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study investigated how agricultural technologies influenced youth livelihood and employability in Ogun State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey design. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select 480 youths who leveraged on agricultural technologies from Ogun Waterside, Odeda, Egbado North and Ijebu-North Local Government Areas of Ogun State were purposively selected based on their predominance in arable farming. Data were collected using a well-structured questionnaire and oral interviews. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Probit regression. The results showed that majority of the respondents were male (75.8%), married (83.5%), had education (60.6%), access to extension services (52.4%) and cooperative membership (85.4%). Probit regression results showed that technology usage ($\beta = 0.971$, $p < 0.01$), education ($\beta = 1.340$, $p < 0.01$), access to training ($\beta = 0.984$, $p < 0.01$) and income ($\beta = 0.710$, $p < 0.01$) significantly influenced the likelihood of youths' livelihood and employability in the study area. Conversely, high cost of technology ($\beta = -0.621$, $p < 0.01$), poor access to credit ($\beta = -0.452$, $p < 0.01$) and adoption ($\beta = -0.549$, $p < 0.01$) remained barriers to usage. It is concluded that youths with training in agricultural technologies experienced higher income, improved livelihood and employability in the study area. The study, therefore, recommended that adoption and leveraging on agricultural technologies like threshers, solar pumping machines and supportive government policies in place will encourage youth participation in agriculture in Ogun State, Nigeria.

Keywords: agricultural technologies, youth, livelihood, employability

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural technology, also known as agtech or agritech, refers to the application of scientific and engineering principles to improve agricultural practices. It encompasses a broad range of tools, techniques, and innovations designed to enhance crop and livestock production, increase efficiency, and promote sustainability in farming (Afolabi & Osei, 2024). It includes the use of modern machinery such as tractors, combines, harvesters, and other equipment designed for efficient planting, harvesting, and processing of crops. It can also be combination of precision farming technologies such as drones, Global Positioning Systems, sensors, and data analytics to optimize resource use (water, fertilizer, pesticides) and improve crop yields (Ogboru, 2025). It can be the use of information and communication technology (ICT) such as mobile devices, software, and cloud-based platforms for farm management, market access, and information sharing as well as renewable energy technologies like implementing solar, wind, and other renewable energy sources to power farms and reduce reliance on fossil fuels in order to meet the growing global demand for food by optimizing yields and efficiency and minimizing water usage, reducing fertilizer and pesticide application, and promoting soil health as

well as reducing costs, increasing productivity, and improving market access for farmers (Adeolu *et al.*, 2025). Digital technologies, an aspect of agricultural technology, in agricultural production refers to the use of electronic devices, software, and networks to optimize farming practices, increase efficiency, and improve crop yield (Ghazi *et al.*, 2021).

The agricultural sector remains a central pillar of Nigeria's economy, employing nearly 70 % of the population and contributing 22.35 % to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in 2021 (Adeoti *et al.*, 2021). Agricultural technologies and digital tools, including mobile applications, precision agriculture, and blockchain technology, have been recognized for their potential to transform agricultural practices, leading to improved yields, resource management, and market access to farmers all over the world and including in the Southwestern Nigeria (Ogboru, 2025). These technologies can significantly reduce labour costs and improve efficiency. The integration of digital technologies in agriculture as buttressed by Oluwasemilore and Oluwasola (2021) facilitate information dissemination, empowering farmers with timely data on weather conditions, pest management, and market prices. Furthermore, mobile apps have been developed to connect farmers to agronomists

and experts, fostering knowledge exchange and improving farming techniques (Ihenacho et al., 2021).

Despite the sector's importance for economic growth, poverty reduction, and national food supply, food insecurity remains widespread and persistent (Ogunniyi *et al.*, 2022). The vulnerability of smallholders is compounded by their dependence on rain-fed agriculture, poor access to inputs and credit, and weak post-harvest infrastructure (Eze *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, the lack of effective agricultural technologies and digital devices leads to lower food production and high post-harvest losses, reducing both farmers' income and food availability (Adeolu *et al.*, 2025). The Ogun State, with its fertile soil and favorable climate, has immense potential for agricultural growth, but farmers in the region face numerous challenges, including limited access to information, inadequate financial services, poor market linkages, climate change, low agricultural productivity among others (Ogunniyi *et al.*, 2022). The low agricultural production in the region could be as a current of the current practice among farmers in the region. Most farmers rely heavily on traditional farming systems which have impacted negatively on their farm output. This situation calls for targeted interventions that address the barriers to agricultural technology adoption and embrace comprehensive approaches to enhance the effective utilization of technologies by farmers in the region (Adeoti *et al.*, 2021). Understanding these imbalances between food production and rapid population growth provided insights into how agricultural technologies can be leveraged to improve youth livelihood and employability in Ogun State, and by extension to Nigeria's youths and agricultural industries.

Objectives of the study

The main objective is the influence of agricultural technologies on youth livelihood and employability in Ogun State.

1. describe the socio-economic characteristics of youth farmers in Ogun State;
2. identify types of agricultural technologies used by the youth farmers in the study area;
3. determine the influence of agricultural technologies on youth livelihood and employability in the study area; and
4. identify the challenges limiting adoption and usage of agricultural technologies among youth farmers in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Ogun State. The state is located in Southwestern Nigeria, Ogun State covers

16,762 square kilometres. It borders Lagos State to the south, Oyo and Osun states to the North, Ondo State to the east and the Republic of Benin to the west. Agriculture is one of the primary occupations of the people in the State. Ogun State is endowed with natural resources which include an extensive fertile soil suitable for agriculture and mineral deposits. The climate and soil of the state are suitable for the cultivation of a wide range of food crops which include rice, maize, cassava, yam and banana and cash crops which include cocoa, kolanut, rubber, palm oil and palm kernels. Ogun State is one of the largest producers of kolanut, timber, rubber and ofada rice in Nigeria (Adeolu et al., 2025). There are twenty (20) Local Government Areas (LGAs) in the state and Ogun State Agricultural Development Project (OGADEP) is sub-divided into four (4) agricultural zones namely Abeokuta, Ijebu-Ode, Ikenne and Ilaro (Ogun State Diary, 2025).

A descriptive research design of survey type was adopted for this study in form of well-structured questionnaire and oral interviews were used to elicit information from the respondents.

The instrument was face validated by four experts, made up of two lecturers from the Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State and two lecturers from Department of Crop Science, University of Ibadan, Oyo State. The reliability of the instrument was determined by administering the questionnaire to arable farmers in Ibadan, Oyo State which was outside the study area. The data generated was analysed using Cronbach alpha reliability test which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.84%, and the instrument was adjudged reliable. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 480 respondents.

At first stage, youth farmers who had gone through digital registration under the OGFIMS development project led by IITA in the four Agricultural Development Project zones of Ogun State were randomly selected. At second stage, purposive selection of four LGAs notable for food production namely Ogun Waterside, Odeda, Egbado North and Ijebu North LGAs was done. At third stage, simple random sampling technique was employed to select 120 registered youth farmers who leveraged on agricultural technologies from each of the four selected LGAs.

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts; percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to describe the socio-economic characteristics of respondents; various types of agricultural technologies used was measured using Yes and No rating; influence of agricultural technologies on youth livelihood and employability

was measured on a 4-Likert scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree and had means (\bar{x}) of 2.5 as cut-off point for decision making. Challenges limiting adoption and usage of agricultural technologies among youth farmers were measured on a three-point response options of Severe (2), Mild (1) and Not a challenge (0) and had individual means (\bar{x}) of 1.5 as cut-off point for decision making. Probit Regression was used to determine the socio-economic parameters of the respondents.

Model Specification: Probit regression equation: Socio-economic parameters on the influence of agricultural technologies on youth livelihood and employability.

$$P(Y=1/\chi) = Q(\chi\beta)$$

Y = Binary outcome; β = Vector of coefficient; Q = Cumulative distribution function

For this study $Y_1 = f(\chi_i)$

$$Y_1 = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, X_9, X_{10}, X_{11}, X_{12}, X_{13} \text{ and } X_{16})$$

The model's specification are as follows:

β_0 ,

$$\beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + \beta_9 X_9 + \beta_{10} X_{10} + \beta_{11} X_{11} + \beta_{12} X_{12} + \beta_{13} X_{13} + \beta_{16} X_{16}$$

Where Y = (yes = 1; no = 0)

X_1 = Years of Age, X_2 = Sex (where Female = 0 and Male = 1),

X_3 = Education (if educated = 1, Otherwise = 0), X_4 = Farm size (The number of hectares)

X_5 = Household size (The number of household members)

X_6 = Farming experience (The number of years spent farming)

X_7 = Seasonal income (Total amount of income per household in a planting season)

X_8 = Membership of cooperative (if yes = 1, no = 0), X_9 = Extension contact (if yes = 1, no = 0)

X_{10} = Sources of information (Family/Friends = 1, Otherwise = 0)

X_{11} = Access to training (if yes = 1, no = 0)

X_{12} = Hardware-farm machines (If yes = 1, no = 0)

X_{13} = Technology usage (The number of technologies used)

X_{14} = Cost of technology (if expensive = 1, Otherwise = 0), X_{15} = Access to credit (if yes = 1, no = 0)

X_{16} = Adoption of technology (if yes = 1, Otherwise = 0)

β_0 is the intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_{16}$ are the coefficients to be estimated.

Note: If Y is the dependent variable, it means all the socio-economic parameters ($X_1 - X_{16}$) are the independent variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result in Table 1 shows that majority (75.8%) of the youth farmers were male. This implies that both male and female young farmers leveraged agricultural technologies to enhance food production in the study area. The majority (83.5%) were married, 53.8% had arable farming as their primary occupation, 72.9% sourced for information through relatives and friends, 65.8% through radio, 41.9% through television, 61.3% through internet/social media and 52.5% through extension agents while 22.9% through research institutes. This aligns with the findings of Hashmi *et al.*, (2022) who found that married individuals often demonstrate increased responsibility towards adopting sustainable agricultural practices to secure family livelihoods. The mean and standard deviations of respondents' age were 27.5 ± 6.9 years, education 8.6 ± 4.4 years, households size 5 ± 2 people, farming experience 8 ± 4 years, seasonal income $\text{N}1,276,920 \pm \text{N}451,236$ and number of technology usage were 5 ± 2 technologies respectively. Similar findings were reported by Akinrotimi *et al.*, (2022), who emphasized that educational attainment, household size and income significantly facilitate the uptake of innovative technologies by enhancing understanding, awareness, and practical implementation capacity. Previous studies, including those by Adeolu *et al.*, (2025) highlights that farm size and access to credits can significantly impact the adoption of resource-intensive technologies due to scalability issues.

Socio-economic characteristics of the youth farmers in the study area

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of the youth farmers (n=480)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Age (years)			27.5	6.9
< 20	24	5.0		
20 – 30	176	36.7		
> 30	280	58.3		
Sex				
Male	364	75.8		
Female	116	24.2		
Marital status				
Single	66	13.8		
Married	401	83.5		
Divorced	13	2.7		
Years of formal education			8.6	4.4
No Formal	189	39.4		
1- 6yrs	121	25.2		
7 – 12yrs	149	31.0		
> 13yrs	21	4.4		
Household size (persons)			5	2
1 - 3	66	13.8		
4 - 6	205	42.7		
> 6	209	43.5		
Primary occupation				
Arable farming	258	53.8		
Cassava processing	74	15.4		
Rice processing	60	12.5		
Produce marketing	38	7.9		
Civil servant	21	4.4		
Artisan	29	6.0		
Sources of information				
Relatives/Friends	350	72.9		
Radio	316	65.8		
Television	201	41.9		
Internet/Social media	294	61.3		
Extension agents	252	52.5		
Research institutes	110	22.9		
Farming experience (years)			8	4
0 - 5	33	6.9		
6 - 10	250	52.1		
> 10	197	41.0		

Farm size (hectares)				
< 1 hectare	100	20.8		
1 – 2 hectares	120	25.0		
3 – 4 hectares	226	47.1		
> 4 hectares	34	7.1		
Sources of capital				
Personal savings	471	98.1		
Loan from Cooperative	453	94.4		
Government grant	116	24.2		
Bank loan	60	12.5		
Group contribution (Esusu)	412	85.8		
Salary	21	4.4		
Seasonal income (₦)			₦1,276,920.00	₦ 451,236.01
0 – 1, 000,000	101	21.0		
1, 000,001 – 1, 500,000	123	25.6		
1, 500,001 – 2, 000,000	222	46.3		
> 2, 000, 001	34	7.1		
Membership of cooperative				
Yes	453	94.4		
No	27	5.6		
Access to extension services				
Yes	252	52.5		
No	228	47.5		
Access to training				
Yes	267	55.6		
No	213	44.4		
Number of technologies used			5	2
1 – 3 technologies	53	11.0		
4 – 6 technologies	201	41.9		
> 6 technologies	226	47.1		
Types of Technologies used				
Hardware-farm machines	249	51.9		
Software apps	231	48.1		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The findings also indicate that cooperative membership (94.4%), access to extension services (52.5%) and access to training (55.6%) are prevalent among the respondents. Cooperative and association membership and credit access play a pivotal role in promoting innovation adoption due to access to resources, training and knowledge sharing (Afolabi & Osei, 2024). It could also be noted that majority

(51.9%) of the respondents used hardware-farm machines to carry out some farm operations. This supports the findings of Akinrotimi et al., (2022) reported that adoption of digital devices into agricultural services significantly influence marketability of perishable farm produce through sales platforms, online markets and online orders.

Types of Agricultural Technologies

Table 2: Distribution of respondents on the types of agricultural technologies used

Technologies	Frequency	Percentage
Tractor mounted-slasher	34	7.1
Disc plough and harrow	34	7.1
Seed treaters	319	66.5
Knapsack sprayers	346	72.1
Nursery trays	260	54.2
Drip irrigation kits	35	7.3
Solar irrigation water pumps	35	7.3
Rice threshers	60	12.5
Cassava pressers	74	15.4
Grinding machines	237	49.4
Nylon sealers	134	27.9
Solar panels/bulbs	75	15.6
Software apps	231	48.1

Source: Field survey, 2025 Note: Yes (1), No (0)

Result in Table 2 clearly identifies the types of agricultural technologies adopted and used by youth farmers for livelihood and employability in Ogun State. Knapsack sprayers (72.1%), seed treaters (66.5%), nursery trays (54.2%), grinding machines (49.4%), software apps (48.1%), nylon sealers (27.9%), solar panels/bulbs (15.6%), frying pots (15.4%) and rice threshers (12.5%) while drip irrigation kits (7.3%), solar irrigation water pumps (7.3%), tractor mounted-slasher (7.1%) and disc plough and harrow (7.1%). This implies the

respondents used one or two types of agricultural technologies for food production and processing. These results support the findings of Adeyongo *et al.* (2022) on adoption of agricultural innovations among farmers in Federal Capital Territory, Nigeria. Adopting different types of agricultural technologies by farmers like digital extension services can provide farmers with instant access to agricultural advice, prices, and weather forecasts which will ultimately enhance their agricultural production (Afolabi & Osei, 2024).

Influence of Agricultural Technologies

Table 3: Mean rating of the responses of respondents on the influence of agricultural technologies on youth farmers' livelihood and employability

Items	Mean	SD
Technologies help to increase efficiency, productivity and sustainability	3.99	1.05
Digital devices help in data-driven and decision making	3.92	1.00
Blockchain technologies enhance supply and higher crop yields	3.81	0.97
Technologies increase farmers' income and improve livelihood	3.58	0.93
Technologies and digital devices create employment opportunities for workers	3.40	0.90
Technologies create market opportunities for industries that produce them	2.98	0.88
They improve access to innovative market information through platforms	2.81	0.76
They improve access to innovative market information through platforms	2.77	0.74
Mobile extension and advisory services are provided to farmers in rural areas	2.77	0.74
They connect buyers and sellers to reduce post-harvest losses	2.69	0.70
They enable farmers to adopt climate-smart agricultural practices	2.59	0.69
They enable farmers to adopt climate-smart agricultural practices	2.58	0.67
Enhancing supply chain transparency and traceability through blockchain	2.57	0.65
Leveraging on AI and machine learning to predict pest outbreaks	2.57	0.65
Offering virtual training programmes for farmers on best arable practices	2.54	0.65
Creating online platforms for farmers to share knowledge and experiences	2.53	0.53
Using online markets to connect farmers with consumers and reduce middlemen	2.52	0.52
Using online markets to connect farmers with consumers and reduce middlemen	2.51	0.51
Digital soil mapping technologies to analyze soil health for better crop yield	2.99	0.78
Grand mean		

Source: Field survey, 2025 Note: Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1). Mean cut-off point = 2.5

Result in Table 3 showed that the sixteen (16) items had means (\bar{x}) that ranged from 2.15 to 3.99 which is above the cut-off point of 2.5 with young farmers obtaining a grand mean of 2.99 and standard deviation of 0.78. This implies that all the respondents were not far from the mean and from one another in their responses. These results are in agreement with the findings of Eze *et al.* (2021) who emphasized the role

of blockchain technology in enhancing agricultural supply chains in Nigeria. These results corroborate the findings of Oyediran & Tijani (2021) on the role of digital technologies in promoting food and nutrition security in Nigeria. It is also in tune with the findings of Gupta & Rajput (2021) on mobile application for farmers to access weather and market updates.

Challenges Limiting Adoption and Usage of Agricultural Technologies

Table 4: Mean Ranking of the responses of respondents on the challenges limiting usage of agricultural technologies for livelihood and employability

Challenges	Mean	SD	Rank
High cost of technologies	2.91	0.71	1 st
Poor access to credit facilities	2.90	0.66	2 nd
Resistant to change/adoption	2.87	0.62	3 rd
High cost of digital devices	2.84	0.57	4 th
Limited access to internet for information	2.71	0.52	5 th
Limited access to trainings	2.56	0.50	6 th
Lack of technical know-how	2.49	0.49	7 th
Lack of equilateral for loans	1.89	0.48	8 th
Lack of awareness	1.78	0.44	9 th
Inadequate research support	1.65	0.41	10 th
Limited market access	1.60	0.39	11 th
Poor extension services	1.59	0.37	12 th
Low educational level	1.58	0.36	13 th
Unstable electricity	1.55	0.33	14 th

Source: Field survey, 2025 Note: Severe (2), Mild (1) and Not a challenge (0) Mean = 1.5

Result in Table 4 identifies substantial challenges limiting usage of agricultural technologies among youth farmers for livelihood and employability in Ogun State. High cost of technologies (1st), poor access to credit facilities (2nd), resistant to change/adoption (3rd) and high cost of digital devices (4th) were ranked as they emerged as major impediments. These findings are in consonance with earlier studies of Johnson & Williams, (2022) which emphasized the financial burden of digital

technologies in smallholder agriculture significantly hinder technology adoption and usage. Furthermore, limited access to internet for information (5th), limited access to trainings (6th) and lack of technical know-how (7th) are also notable challenges. These factors negatively influence the practical feasibility of adopting and using advanced agricultural technologies and leveraging on digital solutions among arable youth farmers, as supported by recent findings from Ogboru (2025).

Table 5: Probit regression analysis on the influence of agricultural technologies on youth livelihood and employability in the study area

Variables	Coefficient (β)	Std Error	Z Statistics	P-value
Age	0.921**	0.712	1.29	0.050
Sex	0.582**	0.363	1.60	0.050
Education	1.340***	0.954	1.40	0.001
Farm size (hectares)	0.736	0.621	1.19	0.012
Household size	1.025	0.978	1.05	0.020
Farming experience (years)	0.979	0.792	1.24	0.000
Income	0.710***	0.694	1.02	0.001
Membership of cooperative	1.121	0.651	1.72	0.010
Extension contact	0.744	0.366	2.03	0.000
Sources of information	1.190***	0.389	3.06	0.001
Access to training	0.984***	0.361	2.73	0.001

Hardware-farm machines	0.834***	0.227	3.67	0.001
Technology usage	0.971***	0.329	2.95	0.001
Cost of technology	-0.621***	0.167	-3.72	0.001
Access to credit	-0.452***	0.191	-2.37	0.001
Adoption of technology	-0.549***	0.238	-2.31	0.001
Constant	-2.994	0.839	-3.57	0.001
Log-likelihood	-49.93			
LR chi ² (16)	60.86			
Prob > chi ²	0.0000			
Number of observations	480			
Pseudo R ²	0.421			
Correctly Predicted Cases (%)	81.9%			

Source: Field Survey, 2025 Significant at ***1%, **5%

The probit regression results (Table 5) clearly established that sources of information ($\beta = 1.190, p < 0.01$), technology usage ($\beta = 0.971, p < 0.01$), education ($\beta = 1.340, p < 0.01$), access to training ($\beta = 0.984, p < 0.01$), hardware-farm machines ($\beta = 0.834, p < 0.01$) and income ($\beta = 0.710, p < 0.01$) positively influenced the likelihood of youth farmers' livelihood and employability in the study area. This finding corroborates the findings of Ogboru (2025), who discovered that farmers' socio-economic characteristics and extension agents are capable of using digital technologies to enhance agricultural production in southwestern Nigeria. This finding also support the findings of Hashmiu *et al.*, (2022) whose findings concluded that cash crops and food security can be encouraged by massive arable production which is achievable by promoting digital solutions and green agriculture in Ogun State. Afolabi & Osei (2024) found out that predictive tools and smart farming technologies boost cassava production in Nigeria. The negative correlation between high cost of technology ($\beta = -0.621, p < 0.01$), poor access to credit ($\beta = -0.452, p < 0.01$) and adoption ($\beta = -0.549, p < 0.01$) indicates barriers to usage of agricultural technologies, a phenomenon similarly reported by Ogunniyi *et al.*, (2022). Conversely, age ($\beta = 0.921, p < 0.05$) and sex ($\beta = 0.582, p < 0.05$) significantly bolster adoption and usage of agricultural technologies, reinforcing the critical role age and gender play in supporting technological advancements, as found by Peterson & James (2021). This aligns with observations by Eze *et al.*, (2021), who highlight younger farmers' propensity towards innovation and technology adoption. R² was 0.42 which means that 42% level of variation in the influence of agricultural technologies on youth farmers' livelihood and employability in Ogun State, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that leveraging on agricultural technologies had positively influenced youth farmers' livelihood and employability in Ogun State. Youth farmers with education, access to training, credit facilities, source of information and agricultural technologies had increasing income, improved crop yields, reduced waste and enhanced their livelihood and employability while high cost of technologies, poor access to credit, resistance to adoption/change, limited access to internet, to trainings and lack of technical know-how remained major challenges.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the study recommended the followings:

1. Adoption and leveraging on agricultural technologies like threshers, solar pumping machines, grading /packaging equipment and access to credit facilities with supportive government policies should be put in place to encourage massive youth participation in agriculture.
2. Farmers should explore alternative funding options such as cooperative savings schemes, partnership with private investors and reinvesting profits into technology upgrades instead of relying solely on government credit facilities.
3. Extension services should be strengthened to support the youth farmers with necessary trainings on technology usage.
4. To improve livelihood and increase employability chances, training programmes on new technologies should be regularly organized for youth farmers to arouse their interest in agriculture and bolster crop yields.

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